

Data Science for Fighting Environmental Crime

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Abstract. The rise of environmental crimes has become a major concern globally as they cause significant damage to ecosystems, public health and result in economic losses. The availability of vast sensor data provides an opportunity to analyze environmental data proactively. This helps to detect irregularities and uncover potential criminal activities. This paper highlights the critical role played by machine learning (ML) and remote sensing technologies in the continuously evolving scenarios of environmental crime. By examining some case studies on detecting illegal fishing, illegal oil spills, illegal landfills, and illegal logging, we delve into the practical implementation of data-driven approaches for environmental crime detection. Our goal with this study is to provide an overview of the existing research in this area and foster the use of ML and data science techniques to enhance environmental crime detection.

1 Introduction

Environmental crime has emerged as a pervasive and escalating threat in recent years, inflicting substantial global damage. Innovative approaches are necessary to combat illegal activities such as illegal fishing, illegal logging, hazardous waste disposal, and the detection of oil spills. These illicit activities have reached alarming levels, and authorities worldwide struggle to address this multi-faceted problem as environmental criminals exploit vulnerabilities in regulatory frameworks and geographical boundaries. As a result, urgent action is needed to combat environmental crime and protect the natural resources crucial for our planet's well-being.

Criminal networks involved in environmental crimes generate significant profits and inflict financial losses within the European Union (EU). These illicit activities cost the EU millions of euros yearly, hampering sustainable development efforts. Europol's assessment in 2016 estimated the economic toll of environmental crime within the EU to range between €76-218 billion, with a rising trend [6]. The World Bank's 2019 estimation revealed a global annual economic loss of €1-2 trillion from wildlife trafficking, illegal logging, and EU fishing. Environmental crime networks within the EU generate millions of euros in annual losses.

Combating environmental crime, ranked the fourth-largest global criminal activity, is a pressing concern for authorities and law enforcement agencies [24]. The increasing sophistication of criminal networks operating across borders poses significant challenges. However, advancements in machine learning and remote sensing technologies offer promising solutions. Utilizing data stream mining techniques, these technologies enable real-time processing of large-scale data streams, including satellite imagery and geospatial remote sensing data. The scientific community has made significant progress in detecting illegal activities through diverse approaches, leveraging advancements in remote sensing, information and communication technologies, and machine learning algorithms.

Our research endeavours address the distinctiveness of each environmental crime, recognizing the diverse nature of these illicit activities. Each dedicated section provides a concise yet comprehensive overview of some notable approaches to tackling these crimes. By delving into the intricacies of each crime, we shed light on the innovative techniques that offer the potential for an expedient response to the challenges at hand, focusing on the application of streaming data. We aim to contribute to the collective understanding and advancement in environmental crime detection, fostering an environment of immediate action and effective mitigation strategies.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 overviews common data sources and employed methods. Section 3 describes approaches for five different types of environmental crimes: detection of oil spills, illegal fishing, illegal logging and illegal landfills, and monitoring air pollution. In Section 4, we highlight the main findings of this study, reporting still open challenges. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2 Data and Methods

Environmental data's continuous and dynamic nature poses unique challenges for traditional data science techniques. Environmental data streams are dynamic, large, and subject to concept drift, requiring new techniques for incremental learning and adaptation [2]. Real-time monitoring and analysis of environmental data streams are crucial for understanding and addressing environmental challenges. By leveraging data stream mining techniques, researchers and practitioners can extract valuable insights from the continuous stream of environmental sensor data. This enables effective decision-making, early anomaly detection, and proactive strategies for environmental conservation.

The rapid growth in data stream mining, focused explicitly on environmental sensors, highlights the need for novel methodologies and algorithms to handle the unique characteristics and complexities of environmental data streams. Additionally, integrating temporal, quantitative, and qualitative data sources is vital for building reliable assessment and predictive models. Satellite remote sensing has proven to be an efficient tool for Earth surveying over the past five decades [4]. Remote observations can be used to detect illegal activities and monitor pollution, but they face ongoing challenges in separating signals from noise and ac-

curate calibration [4]. Obtaining accurate and comprehensive ground truth data for training and validation is also challenging. Collecting ground truth samples, for instance, during actual oil spill incidents, is logistically difficult, and obtaining representative and diverse training datasets is crucial for developing robust detection algorithms.

The choice of the appropriate methodology also depends on the nature of the environmental crime being studied and the characteristics of the data involved. Oil spill detection techniques often rely on synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images as the primary data source. These methods typically involve binary segmentation to identify dark spots indicating oil spills, followed by feature extraction from segmented areas and subsequent classification as oil slicks or look-alikes [12]. To detect forest disturbances, researchers have explored using wireless sensor networks (WSNs) combined with sound and vibration sensors [16]. These sensors can detect chainsaw sounds, while vibration sensors pinpoint the location of logging activities. Researchers have combined dense time series observations from optical satellites (e.g., Landsat 8) and SAR satellites (e.g., Copernicus Sentinel-1). The integration of optical and SAR data enhances the temporal frequency of observations and leverages complementary information from different sensors, improving the accuracy of forest change detection and oil spill detection. Authorities combat illegal fishing by leveraging Geographic Information System (GIS) data for enhanced enforcement. GIS enables spatial data collection, analysis, and visualization, including vessel movements and fishing activities. By integrating satellite imagery, Automatic Identification System (AIS) data, and radar systems, authorities can track and monitor vessel positions in real-time, identifying suspicious or unauthorized fishing vessels.

The literature review conducted for this work demonstrates that researchers are actively integrating various data sources, including satellite imagery, acoustic data, and GIS and AIS data, with advanced machine learning and deep learning techniques. These interdisciplinary approaches reflect the growing understanding of combining multiple technologies to gain insights into environmental crimes. The findings of these studies lead us to conclude that such integrated approaches are instrumental in enhancing surveillance, detection, and conservation efforts.

3 Applications

We now delve more into some of the scientific work carried out on each type of environmental crime we have selected. We explore the data types and techniques and investigate the potential use of data stream mining in these efforts.

3.1 Oil Spill Detection

Oil spills have significant environmental implications, causing ecological damage, disrupting marine life cycles, and posing substantial risks [1]. Detecting and monitoring ocean oil spills is crucial for informed decision-making and effective countermeasures [1]. While accidents on offshore oil platforms, refineries, and

pipelines contribute to oil spills, they account for only a small portion (5%) of total oil pollution globally. The majority (95%) of oil pollution stems from illegal discharges by ships seeking to dispose of oil residues inexpensively, as supported by various studies, including those conducted by the European Space Agency [1]. Various methods, such as zone segmentation, edge detection, and threshold segmentation, have been used for oil spill detection. However, currently, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques based on artificial intelligence (AI) play a significant role in accurately detecting and monitoring oil spills. Active microwave sensors, like Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), are highly effective for monitoring oil spills. SAR captures two-dimensional images reflecting surface microwave backscattering properties, detecting oil slicks by identifying dark spots resulting from reduced radar backscatter and Bragg wave dampening [26]. SAR’s advantage lies in its all-weather capability, operating effectively under various weather and illumination conditions. Unlike optical sensors dependent on sunlight, SAR emits microwave signals and measures the backscattered signals. This enables continuous monitoring and detection of oil spills unaffected by cloud cover, darkness, or atmospheric conditions [12]. Getting accurate ground truth data for training and validation is tough. In Figure 1, we have two SAR images from the ESA dataset: one with a real oil spill and the other with a look-alike scenario. Collecting ground truth samples, as shown in Figure 2, is complicated but crucial for reliable detection algorithms.

Fig. 1: SAR images from the ESA dataset: (a) Oil spill, (b) Look-alike [1].

Researchers have integrated various data sources and sensor modalities to enhance oil spill detection, including SAR images, optical satellite imagery, infrared data, and environmental variables. Neural networks, particularly deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs), have shown promise in feature extraction, classification, and semantic segmentation tasks, enabling pixel-wise identification of oil spills and other classes in SAR imagery [12].

The research in [25] demonstrates the potential of deep learning models based on polarimetric features for oil spill detection. It introduces the BO-DRNet model, utilizing ResNet-18 as the backbone in DeepLabv3+ and Bayesian Optimization (BO) for hyperparameter optimization. Experimental evaluation using RADARSAT-2 data shows BO-DRNet achieves a mean accuracy of 74.69% out-

Fig. 2: (a) Sample of a SAR image and (b) corresponding annotated image. Oil spills are in cyan, look-alikes in red, brown to ships, land in green and sea surface in black [12].

performing other models. The model’s adaptability and robustness are validated with additional SAR images, enhancing feature extraction and the recognition of oil spill pixels.

The paper [1] presents an innovative real-time oil spill detection approach in SAR images using online extended variational learning. The authors employ an online learning framework for continuous data streams, enabling incremental training and real-time detection. Preprocessing and feature extraction techniques are applied to detect dark spots, including geometrical characteristics and texture, with PCA for dimensionality reduction. The online extended variational algorithm updates an infinite Gamma mixture model’s parameters as new images arrive, ensuring adaptability. Evaluation metrics demonstrate high accuracy and low error rates, highlighting the effectiveness of the proposed statistical framework for SAR image modeling and oil spill classification.

3.2 Illegal Fishing

Illegal fishing poses a significant threat to the sustainability of fisheries and marine ecosystems worldwide. Various technologies, including remote sensing, acoustic monitoring, and vessel tracking systems, such as the Automatic Identification System (AIS), have been employed to combat this issue. AIS data provide crucial information on maritime traffic, encompassing vessel identifiers, GPS coordinates, speed, and course. Integrating AIS with Geographic Information System (GIS) data enhances the detection capabilities of authorities, enabling the assessment of vessel compliance, detection of violations, and identification of high-risk areas for illegal fishing. In recent years, machine learning and data stream processing techniques have emerged as powerful tools for real-time monitoring and detecting illegal fishing activities. By analyzing the movement patterns of fishing vessels using data streams and applying machine learning algorithms to identify anomalous behavior, researchers and practitioners aim to

identify illegal fishing effectively. Dynamic vessel trajectory recognition plays a pivotal role in detecting illegal fishing, and AIS data proves valuable in mapping fishing activities. Utilizing the unsupervised nature of cluster analysis, AIS data can label the trajectory geometry and highlight changes in the vessel’s moving pattern, indicative of fishing activity. Moreover, recurrent neural networks and deep learning algorithms are applied to AIS data for trajectory reconstruction, anomaly detection, and vessel identification, contributing to the efficient detection and combat of illegal fishing.

Ferreira et al. [8] propose a method for detecting fishing activity using trajectory geometry and machine learning techniques. The method - depicted in Figure 3 - involves clustering fishing vessels with similar movement patterns and training a supervised classifier to distinguish fishing vessels from non-fishing ones. They employ k-means clustering to label AIS messages based on vessel movement patterns. Three approaches are examined to define the sliding window size, and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are used for time-series classification. The methodology outperforms existing methods and contributes to comprehensive data preparation, labeling, modeling, and validation processes. The authors capture the geometry observed in trajectories to detect mobility patterns and fishing activity. Their unsupervised contribution focuses on chaotic behavior and abrupt geometric changes in vessel movements, while the supervised contribution introduces a lightweight neural network model. Different approaches, such as moving average of acceleration and moving sum of relative course over ground, are explored for incorporating information across consecutive messages. The findings indicate that a fixed number of messages reduces false positives in labeling, while the time-based strategy effectively captures subtle trajectory changes. The results reveal that recent AIS messages carry more significance than distant ones in tracking movement pattern changes. This approach provides valuable insights for monitoring illegal fishing activities.

Fig. 3: Methodological workflow for the end-to-end fishing detection task [8].

In [17], Nguyen et al. address limitations in existing models for AIS data analysis, such as strong priors dependence, clustering method information loss, and inadequate handling of irregular time sampling. They propose a multi-task deep learning framework utilizing RNNs with latent variables. The model includes an

embedding block that converts noisy and irregular AIS data into consistently hidden regimes. These regimes represent vessel manoeuvres, disentangling the underlying information and providing scalable regional or global representations. The embedding block utilizes a variational recurrent neural network (VRNN) operating at a 10-minute time scale. VRNNs incorporate latent variables to model complex time series data. The model integrates higher-level blocks for different time scales, addressing tasks like abnormal behavior detection, vessel type identification, position prediction, and maritime route identification. Employing a multi-task VRNN framework enables analysis of AIS data streams at various scales, facilitating anomaly detection, vessel type classification, position prediction, and route identification (cf. Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Detection of abnormal behaviors in Gulf of Mexico dataset, using global thresholding. Abnormal tracks detected in the test set are in red. [17].

The authors propose a "four-hot encoding" representation for AIS data, combining latitude, longitude, SOG, and COG. This structured representation enables learning of trajectory spatial patterns - Figure 5a. The encoding is processed by an embedding block, which includes submodels for abnormal behavior detection and vessel type identification - Figure 5b. The approach addresses limitations by simultaneously addressing multiple tasks, accommodating large-scale datasets, and relaxing finite behavioral categories. VRNNs capture contextual information and handle noise and irregular time sampling. The model's flexibility and adaptability to different maritime contexts contribute to its effectiveness. By challenging common assumptions, this work provides valuable insights into vessel behaviors and demonstrates operational feasibility for large-scale AIS systems.

Time series classification and clustering are essential for recognizing movement patterns, identifying routes, and detecting abnormal trajectories. The approach in [13] improves upon the limitations of the dynamic time warping (DTW) algorithm used for distance measurement in time series analysis. The researchers propose an adaptive constrained DTW (ACDTW) algorithm that addresses overstretching and over-compression issues by introducing adaptive penalty functions. These penalties enable accurate distance calculations between trajectories and dynamically adjust their correspondence, improving accuracy in measuring

Fig. 5: AIS "four-hot" encoding (a) and VRNN architecture (b) used in [17]

Fig. 6: Continuous trajectories stream using sliding window model [27].

distances. In [27], a dynamic approach is developed for recognizing maritime traffic patterns using AIS data. The technique involves online cleaning, compression, partitioning, and clustering of the data to adapt in real-time to changes in the traffic environment. Expired trajectories are removed and incorporated, making them suitable for processing large volumes of streaming data - Figure 6. The method demonstrates effectiveness when marine traffic routes change, allowing for accurate and adaptable recognition of maritime traffic patterns.

In [11], researchers propose an innovative approach to analyze AIS data by transforming vessel trajectory patterns into images. This method combines computer vision techniques with deep learning models (VGG16, InceptionV3, NAS-NetLarge, DenseNet201) to classify vessel activities based on visual patterns. It offers real-time trajectory classification, regardless of irregular data transmission intervals, eliminating pattern-specific preprocessing steps for scalability and efficiency. Distributed and streaming deep learning algorithms enable low response times and early detection of suspicious activities at sea. This approach addresses challenges posed by large volumes and high velocities of AIS data, potentially enhancing maritime security through automated detection of abnormal or illegal vessel behaviors.

3.3 Illegal Logging

The illegal timber industry, valued at nearly €152 billion annually, is responsible for a significant portion of tropical deforestation and is a magnet for major organized crime syndicates. This illicit trade brings economic, environmental, and

Fig. 7: Diagram of the concept of the logging detection system [16].

social consequences, fueling conflicts among criminal groups competing for market control. Forestry crime encompasses a range of illegal activities, including tax evasion, corruption, violence, fraud, and money laundering. Furthermore, the invasion of humans into forested regions, driven by illegal logging and agricultural expansion, heightens the risk of infectious diseases transmitted from wildlife to humans. This problem is exacerbated when deforestation displaces disease-carrying species into urban areas (Interpol). Illegal logging, the main driver of deforestation, has far-reaching impacts such as habitat loss, species extinction, and contributing to global warming. The illicit proceeds from this criminal activity often fund conflicts and exacerbate social unrest. Addressing this urgent issue requires immediate attention and comprehensive solutions that consider the environmental and socio-economic challenges at hand.

The research community has shown great interest in detecting illegal logging in forested areas due to its profound implications for the environment, economy, and society. Many studies focus on developing automated methods for identifying logging activities in forests. Existing systems frequently employ wireless sensor networks (WSNs) equipped with sound and vibration sensors to detect the operation of chainsaws and pinpoint the precise locations of logging within forested areas. In [16], the authors investigate the application of ML techniques for detecting and monitoring illegal logging activities using acoustic forest surveillance, as illustrated in Figure 7. Their study focuses on training binary models to accurately classify logging activity based on acoustic signals. The approach involved deploying acoustic monitoring stations in different locations within the forest, forming a WSN. These stations were equipped with sensors to capture acoustic data, which was then analyzed using various ML algorithms (e.g. support vector machines - SVMs, multilayer perceptron neural networks - MLP, decision trees - DT, k-nearest neighbors - k-NNs, and Bayesian networks) to classify the acoustic signals and distinguish between logging and non-logging sounds.

Although government initiatives in the Amazon region are endeavoring to combat illegal deforestation, current projects rely on manual operations and complex methodologies. More efficient and automated approaches are needed to cope with the dynamic and intricate nature of the region. Deep learning techniques have emerged as a promising solution, offering improved accuracy,

reduced human effort, and faster results generation. Extensive research has been conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of deep learning in detecting deforestation in the Amazon Forest.

In [21], an approach for accurately and timely detecting forest disturbances in tropical seasonal forests using dense time series data from Landsat 8 and Sentinel-1 satellites is presented. The authors utilized the Random Forest algorithm to predict disturbance probability for each observation obtained from two sensors based on variables derived from a harmonic regression model. By combining the disturbance probabilities from both sensors' data, forest disturbances were detected at the pixel level, achieving an overall accuracy of 83.6%. Integrating Landsat 8 and Sentinel-1 data improved accuracy and timeliness compared to using either source alone. However, challenges were observed in detecting small-scale disturbances caused by logging. The study emphasized the value of dense time series data in detecting disturbances, particularly in tropical regions where rapid vegetation recovery can mask signs of disturbances. The approach relied on disturbance probability and machine learning algorithms to identify and monitor forest disturbances, providing valuable information for forest management and early warnings for illegal logging.

In [18], deep learning techniques, especially deep neural networks (DNNs), were selected for their capacity to learn multiple levels of data representation automatically and extract robust features. The study utilized convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and Siamese networks as specific variants of DNNs. CNNs were suitable for capturing spatial dependencies and patterns in image analysis tasks. Simultaneously, Siamese networks were chosen for their ability to leverage paired input images and generate combined feature representations.

The dataset used in the study consisted of pairs of Landsat 8-OLI images with a spatial resolution of 30 meters. Preprocessing steps included atmospheric correction and clipping the images to the target area. The resulting images had dimensions of 1100×2600 pixels and consisted of seven spectral bands.

In the proposed approach, each image pair was processed by a Siamese network, with individual branches independently analyzing the input patches. The outputs from the branches were concatenated to create a final feature vector, which was then classified to distinguish between deforestation and non-deforestation areas at the pixel level. The deep learning approach aimed to overcome the limitations of traditional methods, providing a more accurate and automated solution for deforestation detection in the Amazon Rainforest. The model learned meaningful representations by utilizing CNNs and Siamese networks and efficiently exploited the information in Landsat images, leading to improved deforestation detection results.

3.4 Illegal Landfills

The proliferation of illegal landfills worldwide, particularly in developing nations, has emerged as a pervasive issue. Several papers have made significant contributions to the detection of illegal landfills. In [10], Hua et al. focused on segregating

Fig. 8: Example of images with different annotated waste dump [23]: (A) tyres, (B) scattered waste, (c) dumpsters, (D) grouped cars.

hazardous waste using deep neural networks in real-time video. Their work introduced a deep neural network model capable of real-time video analysis for detecting and classifying hazardous waste materials. This approach integrates computer vision techniques and machine learning algorithms, enabling the identification of specific waste materials and distinguishing between hazardous and non-hazardous waste. Another notable contribution is the paper by Torres et al. [23], which explores using class activation maps (CAMs) in remote sensing to identify illegal landfill sites, such as the ones illustrated in Figure 8. The study investigates the effectiveness of CAMs in highlighting discriminative regions associated with illegal landfills, aiding in their detection and localization. Integrating CAMs with other remote sensing data and analysis techniques further enhances the accuracy and reliability of illegal landfill detection.

In [3], Devesa and Vazquez presented a mapping of illegal waste dumping sites using neural network classification of satellite imagery. Their work leverages neural network-based classification models to automate identifying and mapping illegal waste dumping sites. Using satellite data and machine learning techniques, their approach offers a practical solution for monitoring and assessing the extent of illegal waste dumping activities. These papers collectively contribute to illegal landfill detection by introducing advanced technologies and approaches, such as deep neural networks, class activation maps, and satellite imagery analysis, thereby providing valuable insights into addressing environmental crimes associated with illegal landfill activities.

3.5 Air Pollution Monitoring

Certain crimes against the environment aren't necessarily committed by certain individuals or companies. There are crimes committed by all of us, together, just by living our normal XXI century modern lifestyle, with current technology. Air pollution is, unfortunately, one of those crimes, and it has been a prevalent issue since the Industrial Revolution. It accelerated the emission of pollutants

Fig. 9: The MoDisNet sensor grid architecture [14].

previously confined to the domestic use of plant and mineral fuels and intermittent volcanic emissions. Approximately 50% of the world's population resides in cities and urban areas, exposing them to higher levels of air pollutants [5]. The primary factors that impact the environment in which we live can be categorized into four major groups: local air quality, climate change, noise, and water resource pollution [7]. Air quality is, therefore, of the utmost importance.

In London, a sensor Grid-based methodology was used for monitoring air pollution levels. Wireless sensors and Grid computing were established as part of a distributed network infrastructure for gathering comprehensive environmental data related explicitly to road traffic emissions in urban areas at low costs. Such a large scale of interconnected sensors, continuously monitoring air quality, could serve as a base platform, supplying continuous data streams for real-time analysis and developing and applying real-time, online learning algorithms that could learn and catch offenders in real-time.

The MoDisNet system involves using various vehicles, such as taxis or buses, to create a platform of environmental sensors. Static sensors are positioned on the roadside to detect real-time air pollution distribution in London. This system consists of a two-layer network architecture (cf. Figure 9): the mobile sub-network formed by Mobile Sensor Nodes (MSN) and the stationary sub-network organized by Static Sensor Nodes (SSN). The MSNs filter the pollution data and perform analogue-to-digital conversion to obtain digital signals. They can also preprocess the raw data by reducing noise, cleaning, merging local data, and more. The processed data is then sent to the nearest SSN, responsible for receiving, updating, storing, and exchanging the data. The sensors used in the MoDisNet Network are GUSTO (Generic Ultraviolet Sensor Technologies and Observations) sensor units, measuring the relative concentrations of atmospheric pollutants in real-time.

MoDisNet is based on developing a "Mobile Sensor Data Grid" for processing, integrating, and analysing data from heterogeneous sensors. Based on the "Discovery Net EPSRC e-Science Pilot Project" [20], a service-based infrastructure was developed to support data analysis from statically located urban pollution monitoring sensors. The nature and number of these sensor networks

mean that, in most cases, the data cannot be realistically stored and then analyzed offline. Most of the analysis must be performed within the network, using computing technologies such as the Peer-to-Peer (P2P) model [22]. This model is viable, as even the most rudimentary sensors will have processing capability, and sensor-to-sensor protocols can be extended to support real-time dynamic execution of analysis and mining algorithms. The peer-to-peer (P2P) network model among sensors allows them to dynamically communicate and share their findings. To meet the high standards demanded by parallel computing applications for transportation, weather prediction or pollution forecasting, reliable methods for storing and exchanging information within this P2P network must be employed. These simple devices are equipped with computational capabilities suited for participation in advanced systems like grids involving central storage while facilitating communication between multiple sensors. MoDisNet's focus on innovative technology involves two equally significant methodologies – creating P2P methods and protocols that enhance kinetics-related "real-time" processing for vast amounts of transportation and environmental statistical data obtained through these devices systems; first; secondly, introducing communication protocols suitable to support dynamic aggregation of real-Time 'Big Data'. These state-of-the-art approaches empower MoDisNet to carry out a broad range of analytical tasks, from data mining in real-time to historical analysis from offline stored information. Centralized data exploration, P2P-oriented distributed database exploration, and integrated database exploration form the three classifications for this system's information scanning tasks. In the MoDisNet system, capturing both the types of pollutants detected by sensors and the spatial information is crucial, as the sensors can be mobile. This necessitates the recording of sensor locations during each measurement. Consequently, analyzing this data requires diverse components, including statistical methods, clustering algorithms, visualization techniques, and classification tools. Furthermore, exploring the spatiotemporal variations of multiple pollutants about each other can be directly conducted using the collected pollution data. However, establishing correlations with external data sources such as weather conditions, health indicators, or traffic patterns holds greater significance. This requires the adoption of innovative, dynamic data access and integration techniques.

4 Summary and Open Challenges

This study analyzed scientific literature on environmental crimes and found that the scientific community has extensively researched the topic, utilizing diverse data types and machine learning techniques. Specific approaches have been developed for different types of environmental crimes, as shown in Table 1. Satellite remote sensing has greatly improved environmental monitoring, but challenges remain in accurately extracting variables, calibrating instruments, and developing affordable technologies [4].

Although satellite remote sensing has broad coverage, it has limitations, such as difficulty distinguishing oil spills from look-alikes due to visual similarities

caused by water surface variability [1]. Complex spectral characteristics and overlapping responses further hinder differentiation [1]. Overcoming these challenges is essential for developing robust satellite-based detection algorithms that may require more frequent reference images for real-time monitoring [21].

Models for traject reconstruction and anomaly detection in AIS data have limitations, such as relying on solid priors and struggling to capture vessel heterogeneity and behaviors [17]. More sophisticated models are needed to accommodate diverse vessel types and behaviors observed globally. Using clustering techniques may hinder capturing the full complexity of AIS data [17].

The lack of available labeled training data for illegal landfills is a significant limitation for training deep neural networks or other classification models.

Air pollution presents several challenges when performing data mining in sensor networks, such as limited resource constraints, the complexity of data collection and analysis due to the mobility of sensor nodes, and the transmission of sensor data in time-ordered streams over the network, making traditional centralized mining techniques inapplicable [15,9,19].

Further research is needed to overcome these challenges and develop more effective and robust solutions for detecting and combating environmental crimes on a larger scale. Addressing the scarcity of labeled datasets, improving generalization capabilities, and tackling other specific limitations are important steps towards achieving this goal.

Table 1: Environmental crimes, data sources, and machine learning approaches.

Environmental Crime	Data Sources	Machine Learning Approaches
Oil spill	SAR images, optical satellite imagery	CNN, DNN (BO-DRNet) [25], Online Extended Variational Learning of Dirichlet Process Mixtures of Gamma Distributions [1]
Illegal fishing	GIS data, AIS data	VRNN [17], k-Means and RNN [8], ACDTW [13]
Illegal logging	WSNs, sound and vibration sensors, SAR images, optical satellite imagery	SVM, MLP, K-NN and BN [16] RF disturbance probability models [21], Early Fusion (EF), Siamese Network (SN), CSVM, SVM [18]
Illegal landfills	satellite imagery, remote sensing data, real-time video data	CAM, CNN (ResNet50, ECA-Net, CBAM) [23], U-net [3]
Air pollution	sensor data	[14][5]

5 Conclusions

The integration of remote sensing and deep learning techniques has made significant efforts to address environmental crimes with improved accuracy. However,

much work still needs to be done, especially in data stream mining. While traditional algorithms have been widely applied to detect environmental crimes, there is a lack of focus on streaming data approaches. Despite this, the scientific community remains committed to finding meaningful solutions for illegal activities like fishing, logging and waste dumping. Effective collaborations between deep learning scientists, authorities, and policymakers are crucial for coordinated responses to environmental crimes. Combining expertise and resources can achieve more efficient and timely crime detection and response. Advanced technologies enhance the ability to detect and combat environmental crimes, strengthening the partnership between researchers and authorities. It is essential to harness the potential of machine learning, deep learning, and data stream mining to develop proactive solutions. As we stand at critical conditions with the potentiality of being a turning point, leveraging the abundance of available data responsibly can impact the fight against environmental crimes and preserve our planet for future generations.

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